
General review of various methods of Water and wastewater treatment

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Abstract

The world's water resources are limited, and according to a pessimistic view, if another world war were to take place in the world, it would be about water and access to water resources.

Therefore, the preservation of existing resources, as well as the optimal use of water resources, will be one of the priorities of international institutions and at the top of the political decisions of governments.

With the growth of cities and the increase in their population on the one hand, and the expansion of industries and factories on the other hand, the issue of environmental pollution is becoming more and more important.

With the expansion of machine life and the lack of attention to public interests, many types of pollution are making human and animal environment unhealthy every day and putting their lives at serious risk, so the issue of wastewater treatment is very important.

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